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शिक्षण आणि समाज

Education and Society

वर्ष ४५, अंक १, ऑक्टोबर ते डिसेंबर २०२१

Year 45, Issue 1, Oct. to Dec. 2021

इंडियन इन्स्टिट्यूट ऑव्ह एज्युकेशन
जे. पी. नाईक पथ, कोथरुड, पुणे- ४११ ०३८

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Development and Social Development through Education'
'सामाजिक विकासातून शिक्षण आणि शिक्षणाद्वारा सामाजिक विकास'
ह्या धोरणास वाहिलेले त्रैमासिक

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Editorial	04
बदलते शैक्षणिक धोरण आणि शिक्षकाची भूमिका	
उदयकुमार शिंदे	07
ऑनलाइन शिक्षण: तथ्य आणि मिथ्य	
वंदना मुंडासे-गौर	13
सातत्यपूर्ण सर्वकष मूल्यमापन: सुधारित नोंदतक्त्यांची निर्मिती व परिणामकारकता	
गीता शिंदे आणि विद्या वायकोळी	20
स्वयंअध्ययन: काळाची गरज	
पद्मजा भालचंद्र कस्तुरे	30
जळगाव शहरातील माध्यमिक स्तरावरील विद्यार्थ्यांमधील इंग्रजी विषयातील भाषण कौशल्याचा...	
केतन चौधरी आणि रेश्मा कोल्हे	38
नवजागरणकालीन विचारधारा के मलयालम औपन्यासिक गवाहीनामे	
हेरमन पी. जे.	45
Self-esteem among Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim	
T J M S Raju and Anupam Pokhrel	52
Active Role of NHRC in the Protection of Child Rights in Covid-19 Epidemic	
Anila	59
Mental Health and Family Life Education for Healthy Family Life	
Manoj Kar and Ashwini Singh	68
The Interrelationship of Education and Technology: An Analysis of 2020 NEP...	
Jabir Yousuf Sheikh and Ranjana Kanungo	81
Quantitative Analysis of Learners Feedback on Information Literacy...	
Charudatta Achyut Gandhe	88
Attitude towards Sex Education among Secondary School Students...	
T J M S Raju and Bhaskar Uprety	96
ऑक्टोबर ते डिसेंबर २०२१	३

Editorial

We are very happy to publish our new issue No. 1 in 45th years of our quarterly journal 'Education and Society' ('शिक्षण आणि समाज'). In this issue, we have included twelve articles and research papers on different topics related to education, which are written by the scholars of different streams. We hope that the members and readers will appreciate this issue, which is helpful in gaining the knowledge and to motivate for contemplation of different dimensions of the education. We have included here five Marathi, one Hindi and six English articles and research papers in this issue.

In this century, we are thinking of total decolonization of education, self reliant education and autonomous education with online education system. Therefore we promote the writers, scholars and researchers in every field especially with education and social sciences for expressing to write for our issue. We are awaiting for the research papers and critical articles on the NEP 2020 regarding the implications of the same.

Along with we are expecting the writings on the issues of autonomy and education, online education, the role of virtual reality in education and the role of robotics in education for our future generation. As we know, we are thinking on the use of Artificial Intelligence in different fields of the human life, so we have to write on the same regarding the future human development with the help of education. We all know that the various new ideas, concepts and terminologies are coming in education for easy learning and decentralized education. We are expecting to expressions on the role of massive open online education. We have to write on these because all these are the flaming issues in current education.

In this issue we can read on the following topics.

Changing education policies and the role of the teachers, the facts and the reality of online education, the importance of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation, the need of self learning, the skills of speeches in English, critics of Malayalam novels, the issue of self esteem among students, mental health and healthy family, protection of child rights, information literacy program, the inter relationship between the education and technology and attitude towards the sex education.

We hope that the readers will send their comments on the above different topics those are included in this issue. We will publish the opinions and the reactions of the readers in our next issue.

Please note that the opinions, conclusions and the findings of the researchers expressed in different articles and research papers are their own. The editor, executive editor and editorial board will not be responsible for the same.

-Executive Editor

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Attitude towards Sex Education among Secondary School Students and Teachers of East Sikkim

T J M S. Raju*
Bhaskar Uprety**

Abstract:

The present study was conducted on the attitude towards Sex Education among the Teachers and Students of Secondary Schools in East District of Sikkim. The data was collected by constructed and standardized questionnaire by Usha Mishra (2008). The data was collected from 50 teachers and 100 students. Means, Standard deviations and t-tests were calculated for the significant values based on the objectives framed. The tables and the findings were framed according to the objectives constructed in the study.

Introduction:

Education is the systematic process of improving learning, knowledge, skill and understanding. Sex education is described as education about human life long process of building a strong foundation for sexual health, through acquiring information and forming attitudes, skills and values about identity, relationship and intimacy. Sex education is openness about sex in society where teachers at schools, parents at home and the department of education have to listen to communication and provide the knowledge about sex education to adolescents. According to WHO (2006), Sexuality is a central aspect of being human throughout life and encompasses sex, gender identities and roles, sexual orientation, eroticism, pleasure, intimacy and reproduction. Sexuality is experienced and expressed in thoughts, fantasies, desires, beliefs, attitudes, values, behaviors, practices and relationships. While sexuality can include all of these dimensions, not all of them are always experienced or expressed. Sexuality is influenced by the interaction of biological, psychological, social, economic, political, ethical, legal, historical, religious and spiritual factors. Sex education is defined as "an age of appropriate, culturally relevant approach to teaching about sex and relationship by providing scientifically accurate, realistic, non-judgmental information. Sex education provides opportunities to explain one's own values and attitudes and to built decision making, communication and risk reduction skill about many aspects of sex"(UNESCO, 2009). Sex education is required for children to

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provide them positive direction, right information which would avoid unnecessary worries and tensions. According to Steinberg (1996), sex education aims to reduce risks of potentially negative outcomes from sexual behavior and equips learners with life skills .It provides knowledge of diseases to prevent transmission of diseases such as HIV/AIDS and other health problem.

An important objective of the school sexuality education is to help young people to build a foundation as they mature into sexually healthy adults. Other goals of school based sexuality education include the provision of accurate information about human sexuality, provide opportunity for young people to develop and understand their values, attitudes and insights about sexuality; to help young people develop relationships and interpersonal skills and to help them act responsibly regarding sexual relationships, which include addressing abstinence, pressure to become prematurely involved in sexual intercourse and the use of contraception and other health measures.

Need of Sex Education:

Every nation, society and community has to work towards promoting the health of its people. When children acquire knowledge, desirable attitudes, values and life skills, they benefit in a variety of ways. These skills help children and adolescents to make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationships, empathize with others and cope with and manage their lives in a healthy and productive manner. Such knowledge and skills can lead to behaviors that prevent disease and injury, foster healthy relationships and enable young people to play leadership roles. In India, like other developed and developing countries, teenagers are becoming sexually active at an early age. This can be because of the early entering of puberty and they face many challenges and opportunities. The atmosphere in which the present day child grows has changed radically and is very different from that of their parents and grandparents. Sexual matters are projected everywhere through different mass media like cinema, magazines, newspapers, radio, mobile phones and advertisements etc. The need of Sex Education in the educational process is unquestionable. Sex Education is the inculcation of the correct moral attitudes towards sex. It means all the educational measures, which prepare young people to meet the problems of life centers around the sex instinct. Therefore it is imperative that parents unfold the true significance of sex in the wholesome development of the young into healthy and intelligent adulthood. Otherwise, adolescents will pick up unwholesome information from the street corner, gutter and the polluted lips of vulgar language. Finally, this type of unhealthy sex knowledge will lead to erratic forms of social indiscipline. In

India, like other developed and developing countries, teenagers are becoming sexually active at an early age. This can be because of the early entering of puberty and they face many challenges and opportunities. The atmosphere in which the present day child grows has changed radically and is very different from that of their parents and grandparents. Sexual matters are projected everywhere through different mass media like cinema, magazines, newspapers, radio, mobile phones and advertisements etc. A survey conducted by the Family Planning Association among school children revealed that the primary sources of information on sex and related matters were television and magazines, not family, friends, or school. Research done by Kahn (1999) in Gambia shows that during the mid-to-late 1950s 8% of adolescent females had intercourse by age 16, in contrast with the mid – 1980s where 21% of female teenagers had sex by age 16. Also in 1990s 50% had sex by age 18 compared with 27% of adolescents of similar ages in the 1950s. Indian society is very much backward to realize the importance of sex education. Since the majorities of the people reside in the rural area and are ignorant and illiterate, it is very difficult to teach and enlighten the public in this area. It is also pointed out that many young people approach adulthood faced with conflicting and confusing messages about sexuality and gender and this is often exacerbated by embarrassment, silence and disapproval of open discussion of sexual matters by adults, including parents and teachers at the very time when it is most needed. Reis & Seidl (1989), Shetty et al. (1997) and Mahajan & Sharma (2005) in their study also found that parents were generally uncomfortable in talking to their children about human sexuality and mothers were reluctant to talk about sex education to their daughters as they found it embarrassing to discuss these issues. It is believed that adolescents who were able to discuss are less likely to be involved in sex than those who do not communicate with parents and teachers. The importance of sex education as a means of developing healthy attitudes can be proved on various accounts. Many educationists agree that school is the best place to administer formal sex education to children.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with regard to gender.
2. To study the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with regard to class.
3. To study the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with regard to management.
4. To study the attitude of secondary school teachers towards sex education with regard to gender.

5. To study the attitude of secondary school teachers towards sex education with regard to subject handling.
6. To study the attitude of secondary school teachers towards sex education with regard to management.

Operational Definitions of the Key Terms Used:

1. Attitude: In the present study refers to a negative or positive feeling that an individual hold about objects, person or ideas.
2. Sex education: In the present study refers to education about all aspects of sexuality that includes family planning, reproduction, sexual orientation, pleasure, values, decision making, communication, relationship and sexually transmitted infections.
3. Secondary school: In the present study refers to a school for students between elementary school and senior secondary school; usually grades 6 to 10.

Delimitation of the Study:

1. The study will be delimited to the senior secondary and secondary schools of East District of Sikkim only.
2. The study will be delimited to one senior secondary government school, one secondary government school and two secondary private schools, (Modern Government Senior Secondary School, Gangtok, Burtuk Government Secondary School, Gangtok, Prashanti Vidya Mandir Secondary School, Gangtok and Kyi-De-Khang Secondary School, Gangtok) of East District of Sikkim only.

Methodology of the Study:

The methodology of the study comprises research method, population, sample, tool, procedure of data collection and procedure of data analysis.

Research Method: Keeping the nature of the problem in the mind; this research uses a quantitative research by using descriptive research method.

Population: The population for the present study comprises of all senior secondary and secondary school students and teachers of East district of Sikkim.

Sample: The sample for the present study was comprised of 61 boys and 39 girls secondary school students and 32 male and 18 female secondary school teachers. Hence, the total sample for the present study comprised of 150 respondents including 100 students and 50 Teachers. The Sample was collected by "Random Sampling Technique"

Tool: Data was collected through a constructed and standardized questionnaire developed by Usha Mishra (2008) for both students and teachers keeping in mind the objectives of the study.

Procedure of Data Analysis:

Descriptive statistical method was used such as mean, standard deviation, t - test and f - test to find out significant difference between the variables.

Table-1 Comparison between Boys and Girls on Sex Education

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-value
Attitude towards	Boys	61	108.03	9.70	2.06 *
Sex Education	Girls	39	104.61	6.81	

The mean scores, standard deviations and t-value of the comparison between boys and girls on attitude towards sex education are incorporated in Table No. -1. It is observed that the t-value is statistically significant at 0.05 levels. It means the null hypothesis framed between boys and girls is rejected.

By comparing the means of boys and girls, boys' attitude towards sex education is higher than that of the girls.

Table-2 Comparison among Classes towards sex education

Variable	Class	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F-value
Attitude towards					
Sex Education	10th	94	106.61	9.03	0.17@
	11th	3	106.33	5.85	
	12th	3	109.66	2.51	

The mean scores, standard deviation and F-value of the comparison between boys and girls with regard to class on attitude towards sex education are incorporated in Table No-2. It is observed that the F-value is statistically not significant. It means the null hypothesis framed between boys and girls with regard to class is accepted.

By comparing the means of boys and girls with regard to class, there is no significant difference between boys and girls attitude towards sex education.

Table-3 Comparison between Government and Private Students on Sex Education

Variable	Management	N	Mean	S.D	t-value
Attitude towards	Government	56	106.10	7.75	0.73@
Sex Education	Private	44	107.45	10.04	

The mean scores, standard deviation and t-value of the comparison between boys and girls with regard to management on attitude towards sex education are incorporated in Table No-3. It is observed that the t-value is statistically not significant. It means the null hypothesis framed between boys and girls with regard to management is accepted.

By comparing the means of boys and girls with regard to management, there is no significant difference between boys and girls attitude towards sex education.

Table-4 Comparison between male and female teachers on attitude towards sex education

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-value
Attitude towards	Male	32	109.84	11.90	1.38@
Sex Education	Female	18	115.27	13.98	

The mean scores, standard deviation and t-value of the comparison between teachers with regard to gender on attitude towards sex education are incorporated in Table No.- 4. It is observed that the t-value is statistically not significant. It means the null hypothesis framed between teachers with regard to gender is accepted.

By comparing the means of teachers with regard to gender, there is no significant difference between teachers' attitude towards sex education.

Table-5 Comparison among subject teachers on their attitude towards sex education

Variable	Subject Handling	N	Mean	S.D	F-value
Attitude towards	Arts	38	110.76	13.17	1.10@
Sex Education	Commerce	4	120.75	12.78	
	Science	8	112.25	10.57	

The mean scores, standard deviation and F-value of the comparison between teachers with regard to subject handling on attitude towards sex education are incorporated in Table No-5. It is observed that the F-value is statistically not significant. It means the null hypothesis framed between teachers with regard to subject handling is accepted.

By comparing the means of teachers with regard to subject handling, there is no significant difference between teachers attitude towards sex education.

Table-6 Comparison between government and Private Teachers towards sex Education

Variable	Management	N	Mean	S.D	T-Value
Attitude towards	Government	31	110.58	12.85	0.85@
Sex Education	Private	19	113.78	12.87	

The mean scores, standard deviation and t-value of the comparison between teachers with regard to management on attitude towards sex education are incorporated in Table No-6. It is observed that the t-value is statistically not significant. It means the null hypothesis framed between teachers with regard to management is accepted.

By comparing the means of teachers with regard to subject management, there is no significant difference between the teachers' attitude towards sex education.

Findings:

The major findings of the study are:

1. The majority of the students respondents shows positive attitude towards sex education.
2. The male students show higher positive attitude towards sex education than the female students.
3. The general trend of attitude towards sex education among the teachers is positive and favorable.
4. There is a significant difference between the male and female students towards sex education at secondary level.
5. The male students' attitude towards sex education is higher than the female students which means males are more positive in their attitude towards sex education than the females.
6. There is no significant difference between the male and female teachers in east district of Sikkim with regard to their attitude towards sex education at secondary level.
7. The female teachers have higher attitude towards sex education than the male teachers.
8. The majority of total students and teachers are in favour of introducing sex education in the schools.
9. The desired stage of implementing sex education by majority of the respondents is the middle school stage followed by the secondary stage of education followed by the primary stage of education.
10. The most undesirable stage of implementing sex education by all

respondents is the university level; the reason perhaps could be that university level is considered too late to start implementing sex education.

11. The majority of respondents consider sex education through the school syllabus the best method of imparting sex education in the schools.
12. The majority of the respondents want to give sex education separately for boys and girls, than to the students individually.
13. The majority of respondents prefer to offer sex education as a separate subject rather than through different subjects in the schools.

Conclusion:

It is found that the most desired stage of implementing sex education by majority of the respondents is the middle school stage and followed by secondary stage. The most undesirable stage of implementing sex education by all respondents is the university level. Apart from introducing sex education in schools, Government should take the initiative of creating awareness among parents about their responsibility in giving sex education at home.

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